

TEENAGE READERS METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11213465>

Annotation

The communicative competence of students develops on the basis of mutually tolerant relations. The introduction of non-traditional tasks into the course process requires students to use deep and broad thinking, methods of comparison and proofing, applying the transfer of knowledge to a new state. Students can independently analyze, select the necessary one from the General Data Stream, independently formal

Keywords: Education, module, process, communicativeness, knowledge, norm, depth, method, competence, form, communicativeness, teacher, student thinking, comparison.

How can teachers activate students' communicativeness without extinguishing their natural curiosity? This question is of interest to teachers and pedagogues today. Active, group, game, figurative, practical, problem-oriented and other forms and methods of education are necessary. School education and the teacher should be aware of the problems they face in directing students to communicative relations and should pay attention to the following pedagogical requirements for the search for scientific solutions for their elimination: - the teacher's word is the student's can be the main conclusion in mastering the educational material; - the ability of teachers to establish interaction with the student; - the teacher can understand the inner mental state of the student and his opinion in time taking into account; - establishing a tolerant relationship with the student in educational sessions and taking into account the complexity of managing this process; - the teacher's communication with students is a mutual exchange of ideas or learning - the ability to reorganize in connection with pedagogical issues arising from the content and essence of education; clarified educational goals) the teacher's knowledge and skills are sufficient in conversion; the teacher can manage his mental state in the interaction with the student; ability to interest students in z subject, positive qualities, high knowledge and professional skills, students imitating the personality of the teacher as an example, the emergence of a creative attitude in them towards the subject of study; to be able to develop a desire to acquire sufficient knowledge of the academic subject; - the teacher should perfectly study the personal

characteristics of the student, and be able to use personally oriented technologies in this process; - use various methods, forms and methods in training sessions to be able to apply, to be able to adapt to the changes in the content, means, forms and processes of education, to follow it, to be able to control the activity of students in the lesson, etc. A positive solution to these tasks is to express the process of exchange of ideas between the teacher and the student as a target system, and the opportunity is created for the student to achieve the goals he has set for himself.

The development of students' communication skills depends on the following: broadening their perception of the effectiveness of active communication and relationship building; understanding the logic of communication and relationships; formation of communication skills; broad and deep thinking; to make conclusions about social relations, think and express their attitude.

Communicative competence of students develops on the basis of mutually tolerant relations. The inclusion of non-traditional tasks in the teaching process requires students to think deeply and broadly, use methods of comparison and proof, transfer of knowledge to a new situation. Students can independently analyze, select the necessary information from the general flow of information, prepare a project independently. As a result of theoretical and practical study of the problem of development of communicative competence in students, determination of objective and subjective factors related to it, and observations aimed at the development of communicative competence in students, we came to the following conclusions:

First, to clearly consider the need, interest and opportunities to develop communicative competence in students;

Secondly, the correct selection of forms, methods and directions of communication skills development. This, in turn, ensures that the student will be able to correctly assess the situations that arise in different conditions, will be able to enter into a relationship, and will be able to actively and consciously participate in the educational process. Competent approach to the educational process is combined with basic competencies, that is, the educational product and effectiveness are formed. The modular process of education forms an individual educational direction for students and creates a process that is completely oriented towards communication. In this case, the change is not only the standard, depth of knowledge, the method of acquiring knowledge, the form of ability changes, but also their enthusiasm for communication increases.

Research scientist E. N. Zaretskaya believes that communicative activity is a system of consistent actions performed in a certain order, each of which is aimed at solving specific tasks and can be considered as a unique "step" towards the goal of communication. . Based on the concept of the well-known researcher A.N. Leontev, it can be seen that "communicative activity" consists of specific structural components.

A careful study of the nature and structure of communicative competence allowed us to distinguish two levels, which are interrelated and interconnected: the first level directly determines the manifestation of communicative competence in the communication itself, or in the communicative behavior of a person; the second one should introduce pedagogical-communicative values through the unique characteristics of the student's educational activity, his special desire for communication.

Communicative competence can also be understood as a complex description of a student's personality, which includes communicative competences, psycho-pedagogical competences, mental states of a person seen in communication with other people - all this is manifested in a person's communicative behavior.

It is communicative behavior that includes special mental and pedagogical competencies necessary for communication. But nevertheless, the leading place here belongs to the communicative values, which mean the need of the respondent to communicate in order to determine and justify the direction in the student. Also, communicative competence is considered as a separate system of internal capabilities of a person in scientific and pedagogical literature, which is necessary for the qualitative and useful organization of communicative actions in certain situations.

Perfect acquisition of communicative competence should be understood as "readiness to engage in the communication process in accordance with the communicative situation that has arisen in reality." It should be noted that the main indicator of the formation of competence is the ability to express opinions fluently, holistically and logically, in which the ability to understand and respond appropriately to any type of communicative activity of partners in terms of expressive and clear communication. is used.

It is known that speech is the most universal means of communication, because when information is transmitted through speech, its meaning is less lost. It is with the help of speech that information can be encoded and decoded accordingly: the communicator decodes this information in the process of a

speech message. It can be clear for the communicator that the idea expressed in this is clearly understood by the listeners only when the exchange of "communicative roles" takes place.

Speech can simultaneously act as a source of some information, and at the same time, it can also appear as a way to influence the interlocutor. However, to fully describe the process of interaction, it is not enough to know only the structure of the communicative act. It is necessary to carefully analyze the motives of both parties involved in the transaction, their goals and tasks.

Communicative speech is the exchange of ideas between students using speech.

Communicative speech culture is the skillful use of speech by students in the process of exchanging ideas with each other, following the rules of ethics.

The more vocabulary students have, the more free they are.

Clarity of speech is an important sign of communicative speech. Each word in the speech must be fully consistent with its dictionary meaning. The thought that needs to be said will not find its expression. Reality events should reflect accuracy in the speaker's speech.

Words must be clear in communicative speech processes. Speech should be used consistently. The speech must fully cover the idea to be expressed by the author and reveal its topic and main idea. The next important communicative quality of speech is its purity, that is, the absence of extraneous elements in the literary language. The presence of parasitic words in the speech indicates a lack of lexical reserve, perhaps a lack of confidence in the truth of the topic of speech or a lack of information about it, partially removing responsibility for the spoken word. So, communicative competence appears as one of the important features in today's globalization and information society. Therefore, the tasks of researching the ways of developing communicative competence, developing the methodology of developing communicative and active communication skills of the learner in the pedagogical process, and improving the practical ones remain urgent.

In conclusion, it was found that the development of students' communication and communication skills is a factor influencing the development of their communicative competence; the formation of communicative competence in students leads to the correct establishment of mutual relations with others and the development of communication skills; the formation of communicative competence in a student is determined by the development of their social skills.

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